

ISic3397

I.Sicily inscription 3397

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

(?)

Material

limestone

Object

fragment

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2015.11.13 Metcalfe

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Soluntum

Place of origin (modern)

Solunto

Provenance

findspot uncertain

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Solunto, Area Archeologica e
Antiquarium di Solunto

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR137138

1. [---]ος

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645615

EDR 137138

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 58.1055.5

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